

Role of The School Principals in Facing the Challenges They Encounter

Mo'een Ahmad Oudat

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 09, 2021

Accepted:
October 12, 2021

Keywords :

School Principal, School,
Challenges

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5567352

Abstract

This study aimed at identifying the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter. The study employed the descriptive method, and the study population consisted of the male and female school principals, who were working in Qasabat Irbid (Jordan) Directorate of Education (n=209) in the academic year 2019/2020. The sample comprised (168) male and female principals, i.e. (80%) of the study population. The researcher constructed a questionnaire specially designated to identify the role of the male and female school principals in facing the challenges they encounter. It consisted of (36) items distributed over six domains: (improving the organizational climate, performance development, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing the modern educational technologies, and communication with the parents and the local community). The scientific coefficients of the study instrument were obtained through calculating the content validity, where the total reliability coefficient amounted (0.86). The means (M's), standard deviations (SD's) were calculated, and t-test, One-Way ANOVA, were applied to identify the differences between the means and answer the study questions. The results showed that the level of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter was at a medium degree in all the domains. The total mean amounted (3.60) with (72.25) relative significance. There were no differences in the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter ascribed to the gender variable, nor were differences in the domains: (improving the organizational climate, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, and providing modern educational technologies) ascribed to the academic degree variable. On the other hand, there were differences in the domains: (performance development and communication with the parents and local community) ascribed to the academic degree variable, which were in favor of higher than BA academic degree. Furthermore, there were no differences in the domains: (improving the organizational climate, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing modern educational technologies, and communication with the parents and local community). Meanwhile, there were differences in the performance development domain ascribed to the experience years' variable, and were in favor of "Less than 10 year experience".

Introduction

Human societies have realized that achieving civilized progress and advanced development requires the existence of a modern educational system in its organization and content, and authentic in its framework and content (Altahayneh & Oudat, 2018). The world in our current century and at the end of the last century witnessed many developments and progresses in all the walks of life. The rapid development in technology and cognitive production, as well as the large increase in the populations, widely impacted the different aspects of the human life. Therefore, the individual is required to perceive the needs of this century, adapt with the cognitive and technological revolution; and the societies are also required to adapt with them and plan for a new future (Allan et al, 2012). This equally applies to the educational and teaching institutions that should develop rapidly through their workers, who work as one team, to achieve their objectives and the objectives of their institutions as well. Creating change in the structure of the educational and pedagogical systems and the pertinent legislations, curricula and plans, is no longer sufficient to achieve its goals and aspirations. The educational leaders should not lose sight of any type of knowledge and necessary skill they need, which are the foundations of the future success (Nhaili, 2010).

The end of the last century witnessed a new trend in the school management in a routine manner. The school management goal is not restricted to keeping the school discipline and controlling the teaching process according to the schedule, confining the students, and work towards mastering and memorizing the study

materials. Rather, work should be focused on providing conditions and abilities that help the educational process to develop, and help in achieving the prevailing social objectives in the community (Al-Mousa, 1995).

The role of the school management became represented by the principal as an educational leader, who focuses on observing what is going inside the school environment as an educational institution of programs, activities, and educational events, linking them with the local community needs, and contributing and participating in the development and advancement of this community where the school is found. The school principal should own the personal and cognitive ability to influence in others, as his effect expands to the local community, so that he becomes able to create the required change in the community (Alhabeeb, 1996).

Recently, the educational literature has paid great attention to the role of the school principal, because of its great impact on teachers' performance and practices, and the extent of students' educational attainment, in addition to his responsibility to achieve the results of education (Rafeda, 2011). The principal has also multiple roles that all contribute, at varying degrees, in deepening the school mission, improving its performance, and the betterment of its giving. Therefore, the educational leaderships come at the forefront of the roles the school principal burdens. As such, the principal, who performs the role of the educational leader, should perform main educational tasks, including coordinating all the efforts and providing all the facilities and abilities, to achieve the educational objectives and purposes (Rabab'eh & Alraqab, 2019).

The significance of the study is demonstrated by the developments the world is witnessing in all social, cultural and economic fields, the new developments that the educational system is going through, the responsibility placed on educational leaders to develop their institutions to serve their communities, and focus on the school principals' role in facing the educational needs of the future schools. These developments require the school principal to constantly change his role and responsibility in accordance with these developments and continuous changes, and the accompanying changes in the educational institution, to keep pace with the ongoing renewal and development. As a result, it is necessary to change, develop and define the roles, to realize the objectives that the school endeavors to achieve in the social, political, economical and cultures areas. The recent trends that occurred in the areas of the political, social, economical, and cultural life, as a result of the scientific, technological, and cognitive advancement, in which the education sector had the largest share, made the educational management work towards active planning to face the emerging educational needs that may appear later. We can tell that the management, represented by its principal, who, with his thought, creativity and innovation, reaches the rank of the educational leader. The leader who possesses the technical skills that reflect his abilities in dealing with things; the human skills that grant him ability in dealing with people; and the intellectual skill, which relates to the extent to which the principal understands and perceives the goals of the school, and the extent of his readiness to achieve the objectives. Here, we have not to forget that success in achieving the school objectives largely relies on the school size and the personality of the principal. Thus, we cannot achieve any progress in the school work without his leadership (Balhamel, 2015). Based on the above, we have to empower the school principals to take the necessary steps that improve the performance of both the students and teachers to acquire skills, efficacies, and experiences, treat the emerging situations, employ the efforts and energies, and invest the human and physical resources that are available inside and outside the school. In this concern, there is a correlational relationship between the educational management and organization and the success and excellence of the students in achievement, the workers' job satisfaction, their high morals, and the extent of school participation in the local community development (Dahlan, 2012).

Recently, the total quality management (TQM) system and its applications occupied high importance among the workers in the educational field, and the principals, particularly. The system provides improvement and development of the educational and pedagogical services, an environment that encourages the continuous development, promotes the workers' skills, activates the work procedures, and ignites the teamwork spirit. It considers measurement, analysis and evaluation as bases for the educational decision making and taking, and works towards implementing these decisions (Oudeh, 2010; Majeed & Alzayyat, 2008).

The Study Problem

The school, with the powers and authorities it has, bears an important role in the success and development of the educational process. This role requires interaction with the workers and their participation in the different activities. A successful principal is who possesses successful leading traits with the teachers, students, and the entire school workers, and promotes their development to keep up with the accelerating changes that emerged in all the walks of life (Allan et al, 2012). The principal's work is not free from challenges that encounter him throughout the work, where his ability and method of dealing with these challenges come out. Therefore, the researcher conducted this study to identify the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter, through answering the study questions.

Study Objective

This study aimed at identifying the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter.

Study Questions

This study endeavors to answer the following questions:

- 1- What is the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter according to the study instrument domains, namely: (improving the organizational climate, performance development, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing modern educational technologies, and communication with the parents and the local community)?
- 2- Are there statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) significance level in the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter according to (gender, academic degree, experience) variables?

Methods

Study Methodology

The researcher applied the descriptive method, and the study population comprised all the public school principals in Qasabat Irbid Education Directorate, in the academic year 2019/2020 ($n=209$). The sample consisted of (168) male and female principals constituting (80%) of the study population. Table (1) shows the distribution of the sample participants according to its variables.

Table (1). Distribution of the sample participants according to its variables.

	Variable	No.	Percentage
Gender	Males	95	45.5%
	Females	114	54.5%
	Total	209	% 100
Academic Degree	BA and Less	102	45.5%
	Higher Than BA	107	54.5%
	Total	209	% 100
Years of Experience	Less than 10 Years	71	34.0%
	10-15 Years	70	33.5%
	More Than 15 Years	68	32.5%
	Total	209	% 100

Study Variables

The independent variables are: gender (male, female), academic degree (BA and less, higher than BA), and the experience years (less than 10 years, 10-15 years, more than 15 years). On the other hand, the dependent variables are the domains of the challenges that face the principals: (improving the organizational climate, performance development, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing modern educational technologies, and communication with the parents and local community).

Study Instrument

The researcher constructed a questionnaire specially designed to identify the challenges that face the school principals, as viewed by them. The researcher benefited from the following studies in constructing the study questionnaire: (Alqasem, 2010; Alkilani & Maqableh, 2013; Rabab'eh & Alroqab, 2019; Oudat & Altahayneh, 2014; Abu Jame', 2013; Tarawneh, 2015; Al-Hamdon, 2016; and Carol & Edward, 2007). The questionnaire included (36) items distributed over six domains: (improving the organizational climate, performance development, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing modern educational technologies, and communication with the parents and local community). The researcher used a three-grade scale to determine the cultural level among the principals as follows: (1-2.33): poor, (2.34-3.66): medium, and (3.67-5): high. The questionnaire was distributed and collected during the period from 19 Jan, 2020 till 26 Jan, 2020, during the first semester of the academic year 2019/2020.

Psychometric Properties

The validity of the instrument was verified by presenting it to five specialists in physical education, who provided certain comments on it. It was then adopted after carrying out their amendments. The internal consistency coefficient of the instrument, as a whole, was calculated using Cronbach Alfa, which total reliability coefficient amounted (0.86)

Statistical Processing

Data analysis was done using the statistical package for the social sciences program (SPSS), and calculating the means (M's), standard deviations (SD's), and the relative significance. T-test and ANOVA were used to identify the differences between the M's, and Scheffe test for the post hoc comparisons

Results

Questions One: What is the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter according to the study instrument domains, namely: (improving the organizational climate, performance development, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing modern educational technologies, and communication with the parents and the local community)? To answer this question, the researcher obtained the M's, SD's and relative significance of the challenges domains, as shown in Tables (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8).

Table (2). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the level of the challenges that face the school principals, as seen by them, in the domain of improving the organizational climate

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	The principal works towards the stability of the organizational system in the school.	3.86	0.93	77.20	High
2	The principal works towards following up the educational process in the school.	3.72	1.21	74.40	High
3	The principal provides all the needs for the success of the educational process in the school.	3.56	1.11	73.00	Medium
4	The principal immediately interferes to solve any problem that may face the educational process in the school.	3.60	1.02	72/00	Medium
5	The principal is keen to provide administrative communication channels with all the stakeholders of the educational process in the school.	3.55	1.18	71.00	medium
6	The principal distributes the managerial tasks fairly among the school workers.	3.51	1.20	70.20	Medium
Overall Average		3.65	1.11	72.97	Medium

Table (2) shows that the overall average of the level of challenges that face the school principals, as viewed by them, concerning the domain of improving the organizational climate, was with medium M (3.65) and (72.97) relative significance. The first and second items were with high level, and the remaining items were with medium level.

Table (3). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the level of the challenges that face the school principals, as seen by them, in the domain of performance development

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	The principal is keen to follow up the course of the educational process as per the prescribed annual plan in the school.	3.84	1.12	76.80	High
2	The principal is keen to evaluate the workers' performance in the school continuously.	3.74	0.95	74.80	High
3	The school principal is keen to provide modern teaching aids and technologies in the school.	3.67	0.98	73.40	High
4	The principal encourages participation of the teacher in the educational and teaching courses.	3.54	1.17	70.80	Medium
5	The principal is keen to reward the distinguished teachers in the school.	3.50	1.14	70.00	Medium
6	The principal is keen to facilitate the academic qualification of the school worker.	3.45	1.04	69.00	Medium
Overall Average		3.62	1.07	72.47	Medium

Table (3) shows that the overall average of the level of challenges that encounter the school principals, as seen by them, regarding the domain of performance development, was medium, with (3.63) M and (72.47) relative significance. The first three items were with high level, and the rest were with medium level.

Table (4). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the level of the challenges that face the school principals, as seen by them, in the domain of dealing with school workers

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	The principal is keen to deal well with school staff.	3.79	1.13	75.80	High
2	The principal is continuously keen not to differentiate between the school staff.	3.73	1.04	74.60	High

3	The principal is keen to understand the conditions of the school staff.	3.64	1.09	72.80	Medium
4	The principal is keen to define the roles of the workers in the school.	3.56	1.24	71.20	Medium
5	The principal is keen to help the new workers in the school.	3.44	1.16	68.80	Medium
6	The principal is keen to apply the instructions and roles equally to the school staff,	3.40	1.06	68.00	Medium
Overall Average		3.59	1.12	71.87	Medium

Table (4) shows that the overall average of the level of challenges that face the school principals, as viewed by them, regarding the domain of dealing with the school workers, was medium with (3.59) M and (71.87) relative significance. The first and second items were with high level, and the remaining items were with medium level.

Table (5). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the level of the challenges that face the school principals, as seen by them, in the domain of dealing with the students

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	The principal is keen to increase the students' performance in the school.	3.73	0.91	74.60	High
2	The principal is keen to respect the views of the students and their needs in the school.	3.68	1.19	73.60	High
3	The principal is keen to raise the level of competition among the school students.	3.62	1.11	72.40	Medium
4	The principal is keen to provide the general services in the school.	3.49	1.08	69.80	Medium
5	The principal is keen to reward the outstanding students in the school.	3.42	1.07	68.40	Medium
6	The principal is keen to treat the individual differences in the level of the students' performance in the school.	3.38	1.13	67.60	Medium
Overall Average		3.55	1.08	71.70	Medium

Table (5) shows that the overall average of the level of challenges that face the school principals, as viewed by them, regarding the domain of dealing with the students, was medium with (3.55) M and (71.70) relative significance. The first and second items were with high level, and the remaining items were with medium level.

Table (6). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the level of the challenges that face the school principals, as seen by them, in the domain of providing modern educational technologies

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	The principal is keen to provide the teaching aids and devices required to bring the education to success in the school	3.73	0.91	74.60	High
2	The principal is keen to enable the teachers possess modern teaching methods.	3.68	1.19	73.60	High
3	The principal is keen to provide modern evaluation tools for the students.	3.62	1.11	72.40	Medium
4	The principal is keen to facilitate implementing the curriculum content with modern technologies in the school.	3.49	1.08	69.80	Medium
5	The principal is keen to provide teaching aids to the entire school students.	3.42	1.07	68.40	Medium
6	The principal is keen to train and educate the students on using the modern educational technologies at the school.	3.38	1.13	67.60	Medium
Overall Average		3.55	1.08	71.70	Medium

Table (6) shows that the overall average of the level of challenges that face the school principals, as viewed by them, regarding the domain of providing modern educational technologies, was medium with (3.55) M and (71.70) relative significance. The first and second items were with high level, and the remaining items were with medium level.

Table (7). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the level of the challenges that face the school principals, as seen by them, in the domain of communicating with the parents and the local community

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	The principal is keen to communicate continuously with the parents.	3.73	0.91	74.60	High
2	The principal is keen to keep the parents informed about the behavior of their children inside the school.	3.68	1.19	73.60	High
3	The principal is keen to hold periodical meetings for the parents in the school.	3.62	1.11	72.40	Medium
4	The principal is keen to solve the social and psychological problems that face the students, through cooperation with the parents.	3.49	1.08	69.80	Medium
5	The principal is keen to engage the local community in the different school activities and events.	3.42	1.07	68.40	Medium
6	The principal is keen to organize voluntary campaigns to serve the local community.	3.38	1.13	67.60	Medium
Overall Average		3.55	1.08	71.70	Medium

Table (7) shows that the overall average of the level of challenges that face the school principals, as viewed by them, regarding the domain of communicating with the parents and local community, was medium with (3.55) M and (71.70) relative significance. The first and second items were with high level, and the remaining items were with medium level.

Table (8). Means, standard deviations and relative significance of the challenges domains that face the school principals, as seen by them, arranged in a descending order

No.	Item	M	SD	Sign.	Level
1	Improving the educational climate.	3.65	1.11	72.97	Medium
2	Performance development.	3.62	1.07	72.47	Medium
3	Dealing with the school staff.	3.59	1.12	71.87	Medium
4	Dealing with the students.	3.55	1.08	71.70	Medium
5	Providing modern educational technologies.	3.59	1.12	71.87	Medium
6	Communicating with the parents and the local community.	3.55	1.08	71.70	Medium
Overall Average		3.60	1.10	72.25	Medium

Table (8) shows that the overall average of the domains of the challenges that encounter the school principals, as viewed by them, was medium with (3.60) M and (72.25) relative significance.

Question Two: Are there statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) significance level in the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter according to (gender, academic degree, experience) variables? Tables (8, 10, 11, 12, and 13) illustrate them.

Table (9). Results of the T-Test for the differences in the means of the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter, according to the gender variable

Domain	Gender	M	SD	T Value	Sig.
Improving the educational climate	Male	3.69	1.14	0.69	0.490
	Female	3.61	1.05		
Performance Development	Male	3.65	0.98	0.42	0.678
	Female	3.59	1.09		
Dealing with the school staff	Male	3.68	1.15	1.38	0.170
	Female	3.50	1.01		
Dealing with the students	Male	3.59	0.95	0.96	0.340
	Female	3.51	1.08		
Providing modern educational technologies	Male	3.59	0.95	0.96	0.340
	Female	3.51	1.08		
Communicating with the parents and the local community	Male	3.59	0.95	0.96	0.340
	Female	3.51	1.08		

Table (9) shows that there are no statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges that encounter them, that are ascribed to the gender variable. In this concern, T Test values ranged between 0.42 and 1.38, and the significance level was ($p \leq 0.05$) for all the study domains.

Table (10). Results of T Test for the differences between the means of the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges that encounter them according to the academic degree variable

Domain	Academic Degree	M	SD	T Value	Sig.
Improving the educational climate	BA and Less	3.54	0.95	0.65	0.521
	Higher than BA	3.70	0.87		
Performance Development	BA and Less	3.45	0.94	1.23	0.021
	Higher than BA	3.79	1.02		
Dealing with the school staff	BA and Less	3.54	1.13	1.28	0.205
	Higher than BA	3.64	1.10		
Dealing with the students	BA and Less	3.48	1.08	0.80	0.425
	Higher than BA	3.62	1.03		
Providing modern educational technologies	BA and Less	3.54	0.95	0.65	0.521
	Higher than BA	3.70	0.87		
Communicating with the parents and the local community	BA and Less	3.45	0.94	1.23	0.021
	Higher than BA	3.79	1.02		

Table (10) shows that there are no statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges that encounter them, that are ascribed to the academic degree variable in the domains: (improving the organizational climate, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, and providing modern educational technologies). On the other hand, the Table shows statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges in the domains: (performance development, communicating with the parents and the local community), which were in favor of "Higher than BA" degree.

Table (11). M's and SD's in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter, according to the experience years

Domain	Experience Years	M	SD
Improving the educational climate	Less than 10 Years	3.62	1.18
	10-15 Years	3.63	1.10
	More than 15 Years	3.70	0.98
Performance Development	Less than 10 Years	3.78	1.20
	10-15 Years	3.52	0.92
	More than 15 Years	3.56	1.01
Dealing with the school staff	Less than 10 Years	3.54	1.12
	10-15 Years	3.61	1.17
	More than 15 Years	3.62	0.97
Dealing with the Students	Less than 10 Years	3.50	1.08
	10-15 Years	3.55	1.09
	More than 15 Years	3.60	1.13
Providing modern educational technologies	Less than 10 Years	3.50	1.08
	10-15 Years	3.55	1.09
	More than 10 Years	3.60	1.13
Communicating with the parents and the local community	Less than 10 Years	3.50	1.08
	10-15 Years	3.55	1.09
	More than 15 Years	3.60	1.13

Table (11) shows that there are statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges that encounter them, that are ascribed to the experience years variable. To determine whether there are statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level between the means, the One Way ANOVA analysis was applied, as shown in Table (12).

Table (12). Results of the ANOVA for the differences of the level of the role of the school principals in facing the challenges they encounter, according to the experience years

Domain	Source	of	Total	Freedom	Squares	F Value	Sign
--------	--------	----	-------	---------	---------	---------	------

	Variance	Squares	Degrees	Mean		
Improving the educational climate	Intergroup	472.28	4	54.102	1.167	0.316
	Intra Groups	2796.40	570	4.8019		
	Total	3268.68	574			
Performance Development	Intergroup	235.72	4	57.384	0.757	0.012
	Intra Groups	2899.97	570	5.124		
	Total	3135.68	574			
Dealing with the school staff	Intergroup	125.47	4	2.741	2.346	0.101
	Intra Groups	2415.43	570	2.419		
	Total	2540.90	574			
Dealing with the Students	Intergroup	56.54	4	14.235	2.477	0.089
	Intra Groups	3556.14	570	6.142		
	Total	3612.69	574			
Providing modern educational technologies	Intergroup	56.54	4	14.235	2.477	0.089
	Intra Groups	3556.14	570	6.142		
	Total	3612.69	574			
Communicating with the parents and the local community	Intergroup	56.54	4	14.235	2.477	0.089
	Intra Groups	3556.14	570	6.142		
	Total	3612.69	574			

Table (12) shows statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges that encounter them, that are ascribed to the experience years variable. To determine the sources of the differences, Scheffe Test for the post hoc comparisons was used as shown in Table (13).

Table (13). Results of Scheffe Test for the post hoc comparisons to determine the sources of the differences in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter, according to the experience years variable

Domain	M	Experience Years	Less than 10 Years	10-15 Years	More than 15 years
Performance development	3.78	Less than 10 Years			
	3.52	10-15 Years			
	3.56	More than 15 Years	*		

Table (13) shows statistically significant differences at ($p \leq 0.05$) level in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges that encounter them, that are ascribed to the experience years variable, in the performance development domain, which were in favor of "Less than 10 years".

Discussion

The study results showed that the level of the principals' role in facing the challenges that they encounter was medium. This result is attributed to that the school principal carries out an effective role in facing the challenges he encounters. The researcher is in line with A'shoor & Alshaqran (2015) and Oudat & Altahayneh (2014) in that the principal has to work to improve the organizational climate, prepare the proper school environment for teaching, and develop the teachers' work in a way that keeps a pace with the scientific and technological developments. The principal is also required to improve the relations between the stakeholders in the school and the students, provide modern aids and techniques of teaching, and communicate continuously with the local community. The researcher is in line with Casolo et al (2019) in that the school principal has the ability to define the objectives of the educational process, and engage the teachers, students, and the local community as partners in taking decisions pertinent to the educational process development. Our study is also in agreement with those of Altahayneh & Oudat (2018), and Almuqeed (2006) in the absence of the differences in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter, according to the gender variable. Yet, the principals of both genders have the ability to face the challenges they encounter, and also have the ability to adapt with the evolving and renewable developments. The researcher is also in line with Craig (2020) in the absence of differences in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter in (improving the organizational climate, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, and dealing with the modern educational techniques) domains, according to the academic degree. Nonetheless, all principals should keep pace with the modern developments in the educational process, dealing with others, and working towards providing modern techniques, through attending workshops and training courses for all, regardless of their academic degree.

Furthermore, the researcher is in line with Abu Rialeh (2016) in the presence of differences in the level of the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter in (performance development, communicating with the parents and the local community) domains, according to the academic degree variable, in favor of "Higher than BA" degree. This is ascribed to that the school principals who hold "higher than BA" degrees study various courses in school management and educational supervision, which render them more capable and experienced in communicating with others. Furthermore, they conduct research and studies that increase the cognitive aspects with them. The researcher is also in line with the studies of Bhargave & Pathy (2011) and Abu Jame' (2013) in the presence of differences in the school principals' role in facing the challenges they encounter in "performance development" domain, according to the experience years variable, in favor of "Less than 10 years". This could be ascribed to that the school principal is aware of any developments or changes in the world, regardless of his experience years. He can work towards the organizational climate stability, finding suitable climate and work environment, and providing suitable educational aids for teaching. The researcher further ascribes this result to that the new principals are more capable to deal with the modern technological developments, and the advanced educational methods and techniques, and employ them in education.

The researcher is also in agreement with Craig et al (2017), and Klara et al (2008) in that the principal has a major role and ability to deal with the different situations, listen to the teachers' needs and suggestions, provide proper environment to apply the educational activities, use the alternative teaching instruments, and suggest solutions for the problems and obstacles that face the teachers through the teaching process. Study of Al-Sharif (2010) is also in line with ours in that the principal, who is capable to employ the communication skills with the teachers effectively, contributes to providing the services required for the educational process, and solve many of the problems they encounter. Finally, the researcher is in line with the studies of Altarawneh (2017), and Alghaifly (2011) in that the human relations that are based on mutual respect between the principal, educational supervisor, and teachers, enhance trust with the teachers, and motivate them to put in more effort to achieve the objectives of the educational process.

Conclusions

- 1- The school principals have abilities to face the challenges they encounter in the domains of the study i.e. (improving the organizational climate, dealing with the school workers, dealing with the students, providing the modern educational technologies, and communications with the parents and the local community), and how to deal with them.
- 2- Both male and female principals have abilities to deal with the problems they encounter.
- 3- The school principals who have "higher than BA" academic degrees are more capable to deal with the challenges they encounter.
- 4- The recently employed principals are more able to develop their performance to deal with the challenges they face.

Recommendations

- 1- Activating the school principals' role in the school administrative reformation.
- 2- Expanding the school principals' role and their relations with the educational process components (supervisor, teacher, curriculum, and student)
- 3- The school principals should supervise preparing the plans that will be implemented throughout the school year, in a manner proportional to the school capabilities.
- 4- Increasing the number of meetings between the principals, educational supervisors, and teachers in the school.
- 5- Making workshops or training courses for the teachers continuously, to face the scientific and technological developments in the different areas.
- 6- Motivating and stimulating the teachers to develop their performance.
- 7- Conducting studies similar to the current study.

Study Limitations

This study has many limitations. Firstly, the way the researcher chose the study sample, which was the random stratified manner. Secondly, the results cannot be generalized, save on the targeted participants, and in the same place (i.e. public schools' principals in the Directorate of Education/Qasabat Irbid, Jordan). Finally, the study results relied only on the views of the participants themselves.

References

- A'ashour, Mohammad Ali & Alshaqran, Rami Ibrahim Abdel Rahman (2015). Role of the school principal in the administrative reform inside the school, in the light of certain contemporary work skills. *Journal of the Federation of Arab Universities for Education and Psychology*, 13 (2), 65-90.
- Abu Riyaleh, Maha Mahmoud (2016). Reality of the administrative practices of UNRWA school principals in Gaza Governorate, and their relationships to the morale level of the teachers. Unpublished MA Thesis, Islamic University, Gaza, Palestine.
- Alhabeeb, Fahed Ibrahim (1996). Role of the school principal towards the professional development of the teacher. *Educational Sciences and Islamic Studies Journal*, 8(2), 449-488.
- Alghaifaly, Abdullah (2011). Reality of applying the total quality principles in the educational supervision by the supervisors. Faculty of Education, Curricula and Teaching Methods Department, Umm Al Qura University.
- Allan, Mohammad Othman; Dabbous, Mohammad Taleb; Tayyim, Hasan Mohammad (2012). Role of the public secondary school principals in the professional development of the teachers in Northern West Bank. *Dearasat, Educational Studies*, 39(1), 1-16.
- Almousa, Mohammad Shafiq (1995). Role of the school principal in improving the educational activities as seen by teachers of Alkoura District (Jordan) school teachers. Unpublished MA Thesis, Al-Yarmouk University (Irbid).
- Almuqeed, A'hed (2006). Reality of the supervisory practices of the educational supervisors in UNRWA Gaza, in the light of the total quality principles and its development methods. Unpublished MA Thesis, Islamic University, Gaza.
- Altahayneh, Z., Oudat, M. A. (2018). Applying the Principles of Total Quality Management to Colleges of Physical Education in Jordan, *Manarah: human sciences*, 25(1), 168-135.
- Balhamil, Khadeeja (2015). Evaluation of the teaching efficacies level among the elementary stage teachers. Unpublished MA Thesis, Mohamed Khider University, Faculty of Social and Human Sciences, Biskra, Algeria.
- Bhargava, A. & Pathy, M. (2011). Perception of Student Teachers about Teaching Competencies, *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 1(1): 77- 81.
- Craig, J. G. (2020). A short scale to evaluate supervision and supervisor competence-The SE-SC8, *Clinical Psychology Psychotherapy*, 1-10.
- Craig, J. G.; Geaty, H.; Nicole, M. S.; S & Danielle, L. (2017). The Supervision Evaluation and Supervisory Competence Scale: Psychometric Validation, *Australian Psychological Society*, 52, 94-103.
- Carol, A. F. & Edward, S. (2007). Competence in Competency-Based Supervision Practice: Construct and Application, *Professional Psychology Research and Practice*, 38(3), 232-240. DOI: 10.1037/0735-7028.38.3.232
- Casolo, F.; Daniele, C.; Gabriella, F.; Paola, V. & Casolo, A. (2019). Effective Teaching Competences in Physical Education, *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 19(5), 1806-1813.
- Dahlan, Omar (2012). Evaluation of the efficacies of the supporting teacher as seen by the school principals and educational supervisors in Khan Younis Governorate. *Islamic University Journal for Educational and Psychological Studies*, 20(2), 489-519.
- Al-Kilani, Lubna Tayseer & Maqableh, Atef Yousuf (2013). Role of the private schools principals in improving the organizational climate and its relationship to the morale of their teachers in the Capital Governorate (Amman). *Derasat Journal for Educational Sciences*, 41(1), 1-30.
- Klara, B.; Sarah, M. & Lars, O. (2008). Developing a community of practice around teaching: a case study, *Higher Education Research and Development*, 27(2), 121- 132.
- Majeed, Sawsan Shaker & Alziyadat, Mohammad Awwad (2008). Quality in education, applied studies. Dar Safa'a for Publishing and Distribution, Ed. 1, Amman.
- Nahili, Ali Ahmad Abdullah (2010). Role of the school principals in raising the efficacy of teachers. *Damascus University Journal*, 26(1), 137-173.
- Oudat, M. A & Altahayneh, Z. (2014). The Effect of Educational Supervision Styles on Performance Effectiveness of Physical Education Teachers in Jordanian Public Schools from Teachers' Perspectives, *Majallat al-'Ulum al-Tarbawiyat wa-al-Nafsiyyat*, 15(2), 81-100.
- Oudeh, Hadeel Mohammad (2010). The administrative efficacies of the principals of the basic schools in Ma'adaba Governorate, and their relationship to the teachers' morale. Unpublished MA Thesis, Middle East University, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Qasem, Mansour Bin Mohammad (2010). Role of the school principals in activating the educational supervision in the public schools in Jeddah Governorate. Unpublished MA Theses, Umm Al Qura University, Makka Mukarrama, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
- Rababah, J. A & Al-Roqub, K. A. (2019). Assessing the Educational Supervision Styles among the Supervisors of Physical Education from the Perspective of the Male and Female Teachers of Physical

- Education in the Directorate of Education in Al-Qweismeh District, *Dirasat: educational science*, 46(1), 701-719.
- Rafedeh, Alhariri (2011). Total quality in the curricula and teaching methods. Dar Almaseera for Publishing, Distribution and Printing, Ed. 1, Jordan.
 - Al-Sharif, E. (2010). Evaluation of Student, Teacher Teaching Competencies in the Curricula and Teaching Methods of Motor Expression in the Light of Quality Academic Standards, *World Journal of Sport Sciences*, 3 (S), 331-358.
 - Al-Tarawneh, Rawan (2017). Availability degree of the supervision efficacies among the educational supervisors of the science subjects in the private schools in the capital (Amman), and its relationship to the teachers' morale, as viewed by them. Unpublished MA Thesis, Middle East University, Faculty of Educational Science, Jordan.

Author Information

Mo'een Ahmad Oudat

Associate Professor

Faculty of physical education and sport sciences,
Hashemite University, Jordan